

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ezechukwu**FIRST NAME:** Isaac-Ogugua**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8) X

Seven (7) Key Concepts I encountered in the Coursepack 1

1. Avoiding plagiarism in one's writing (EUCLID 2019, 10)
2. Rules for paraphrasing (EUCLID 2019, 13)
3. When not to cite (EUCLID 2019, 15)
4. Validating your writing (EUCLID 2019, 16)
5. The right uses for articles "a" and "an" (EUCLID 2019, 21)
6. No need to over cite (EUCLID 2019, 48)
7. Certainty of date format (EUCLID 2019, 53)

BUILDING THE RIGHT FOUNDATION FOR WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Quantum writing is typically the scarecrow of many (including myself) who nurse ambitions to run doctorate programmes. Many will delay, defer or entirely drop the idea of commencing a doctorate for fear of the avalanche of writings involved to pull through their dreams. But going through Period One Coursepack gradually minimizes this fear for me. This is as a result of the certainty of basic rules guiding academic writing as explained in the Coursepack. The authors, Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, have been able to simplify and clarify a lot of the confusions encountered in academic writing.

The Coursepack starts with the basic rules for essay writing including referencing in Chapter One. Chapter Two focuses on Plagiarism and how to avoid falling into its temptation when writing. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers are discussed in Chapter Three. Chapter Four talks about Literature Review while Chapter Five shows why it is important to have a Style Guide. Chapter Six compares American writing style with the British style. Sample Corrections to Papers are shown in Chapter Seven. Likewise, Chapter Eight showed a CMS Crib Sheet for learning. The Coursepack concludes with

Chapter Nine which displays Latin Abbreviations and Expressions commonly used in writing. All of these chapter contents have helped to build the right foundation for academic writing and for the lessons to stick one must consult the chapters from time to time in the course of this program.

Avoiding plagiarism in one's writing

2) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM IN ONE'S WRITING

Cleenewerck and Gulma minced no words in stressing the importance of good essays as the visible outputs of doctoral students. The authors highlighted key areas to pay attention to in writing academic essays. One of such key areas is plagiarism, which is defined as “using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). As a staff of an academic institution, I know that plagiarism has been the cause of technical knockout for many doctoral students. I was therefore very happy to learn more tips for avoiding the dreadful pothole in an academic endeavour. It also became clearer to me that avoiding plagiarism enhances the chances of new knowledge being produced in every research work, as it ensures that works of earlier scholars are not merely recycled indiscriminately.

3) RULES FOR PARAPHRASING

Paraphrasing is defined as “ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words” (EUCLID 2019, 8). I see paraphrasing as a key test of learning arising from exposure to the works of others. When one is able to recall and elucidate on the information he has been exposed to in his own words, it helps to internalize what he has learnt. An interesting takeaway for me is that even if you paraphrase, you must still cite the work the information came from (ibid.).

4) WHEN NOT TO CITE

Related to the understanding that even paraphrased sentences must be cited is knowing when not to cite (EUCLID 2019, 9). This is an interesting and relevant piece of information for me. Now I know that I need not cite when the information I am writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas. For example, ‘incessant hunger leads to malnourishment’ may not need to be cited since it is a well-known fact that that is a proven consequence of prolonged hunger. Again, I may not need to cite if in the course of my research I come across certain information repeated in many different sources which means it is safe to assume it is common knowledge (ibid.).

5) **VALIDATING YOUR WRITING**

It is commonplace for some researchers to take their initial draft works for granted when they assume that everything is in its place. As has been my experience too, I also neglect to review my works sometimes with the unpleasant result of noticing some errors later. It, therefore, rang deep into my ear drums when I read the advice: when you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right, (EUCLID 2019, 16). Going over one's writing more than once will help to validate what he is talking about in the piece. One way to make this stick is to make a habit of it. Once it is a habit, it can be done without any hassles.

6) **THE RIGHT USES FOR ARTICLES "A" AND "AN"**

The clarity I got from the explanations on the uses for articles "a" and "an" validates the point that quality is in the little details. When not properly used, each of these two articles can disfigure a sentence and can sometimes be very embarrassing to the writer. The maxim that has stuck in me is put "a" before a consonant sound and "an" before a vowel sound (EUCLID 2019, 21). And when in doubt, one should pronounce aloud the word following the article (ibid).

7) **NO NEED TO OVER CITE**

It is comforting to note that one can eliminate multiplicity of citations which may confuse or clutter a piece of writing. As contained in the Chicago Style, it is now possible to ignore the citation of materials already cited in the work one is quoting (EUCLID 2019, 48). This gives room for speed, free expression and neater presentation of an essay.

8) **CERTAINTY OF DATE FORMAT**

Consistency of style and format is regarded as one of the hallmarks of good writing. Inconsistency can stem from use of different date formats in one piece of writing. The Coursepack has been able to show the defining lines between the British and American date formats. While American style goes mm-dd-yy (month-day-year), the British style is dd-mm-yy (day-month-year) (EUCLID 2019, 53).

9) CONCLUSION

I consider the Coursepack an icebreaker, which has helped to thaw my cringed nerves of apprehension prior to the commencement of this programme. Though, I experienced some delays in concluding this first response paper arising from bereavement, it has nevertheless helped to convince me that I have actually started the programme and can only march forward henceforth.

The coursepack is the foundation for this programme, and like every foundation properly cast, ensures that the entire structure will be solid and be able to stand the test of the times. The Pack lends itself to consultations from time to time as one makes progress. It was instructive to learn those rules governing plagiarism, citations, paraphrasing and articles “a” and “an”.

William Strunk in his book, *The Elements of Style*, gives a golden advice under the *Elementary Principles of Composition* (P. 30), which I will take as my paragraphing guide, and he says:

...make the meaning of the topic sentence clearer by restating it in other forms, by defining its terms, by denying the converse, by giving illustrations or specific instances; or establish it by proofs; or develop it by showing its implications and consequences.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Strunk, William, Jr. 2011. *Elements of Style*. Newly Revised and edited by Chris Hong. Elements of Style Press

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.